

behaviour of the salts of mixed heteropoly anion $[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$. The dehydrated salts exist upto 250° after which they are completely decomposed. Insolubility in water of the heated samples, also show the decomposition of the heteropoly salts.

Molecular weight determination: The molecular weight of $\text{Na}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was cryoscopically determined to be 1301 ± 250 in $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ system by the method as applied by Thilo and Kruger¹⁸ and recently by Pope¹⁴. The cryoscopic constant was taken¹⁴ as 1.8 ± 0.1 kg of water per mole.

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Study of Solvent Effect on Kinetics of Alkaline Hydrolysis of Methylsalicylate in Water-Acetone Medium

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A number of papers¹⁻¹⁰ have appeared concerning changes in the rates of hydrolysis of esters in binary solvent mixtures. Some of them^{2,3} have supported the views expressed by Parker⁴ about the rate enhancement by aprotic solvent constituent of the binary solvent system. However, this view has been strongly refuted by some authors^{1,5,6,8,9} and they observed decrease in the hydrolysis rate by several aprotic solvents. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the effect of medium

(water-acetone) on the alkali catalysed hydrolysis of methyl salicylate.

Experimental

Methyl salicylate and acetone of B.D.H. and E. Merck L.R. grade were used and purified by the known procedure. Preparation of solution and other experimental procedure are the same as previous communications^{9,11}. The specific rate constants were determined in different solvent mixtures containing 10 to 70% acetone (v/v) at temperatures ranging 15 to 35° (Table 1). The reliability of k values were found to be $\pm 0.1 \times 10^{-2}$.

Results and Discussion

The hydrolysis of methylsalicylate follows the B_{AC} 2 mechanism in Ingold's terminology¹². According to this mechanism, the rate controlling step is addition of OH⁻ ion to carbonyl carbon¹³. The transition state of the rate controlling step will not only be polar but will have two units of negative charges superimposed on it. The formation of such transition states in case of the above ester hydrolysis must be favoured by increasing dielectric constant of the medium. Therefore, the rate should fall with increasing percentage of acetone whose dielectric constant is much smaller than water. This is in conformity of the experimental observation (Table 1). The decrease in rate with

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS (k) IN WATER-ACETONE MEDIA
 $k \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Temp. °C	Acetone% (v/v)						
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
15	10.2	8.7	7.0	5.7	5.0	4.5	4.2
20	20.4	16.7	13.8	10.6	9.1	8.4	7.9
25	40.3	31.8	24.8	20.0	17.3	15.7	13.6
30	75.0	60.3	49.6	37.8	31.8	27.9	24.1
35	141.3	116.1	88.1	66.7	60.8	50.7	44.2

increasing mole percent of organic co-solvent of low dielectric constant has been observed by Anantkrishnan *et al.*¹⁰. They have noted that in a medium of dielectric constant higher than 10, solvent solute interaction is more influencing a factor than the dielectric constant. It can therefore be concluded that the observed decrease in rate in water-acetone medium is the combined effect of decrease in dielectric constant as well as solvation changes.

Activation energy: The activation energy value (E_a , shown in Table 2) decreases with increasing

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION ENERGY (E_a) VALUES

Acetone% (v/v)	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
E_a (k cal mol ⁻¹)	23.1	22.6	22.2	21.7	21.3	21.1	20.8

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN WATER-ACETONE

Acetone% (v/v)	ΔH^* , ΔG^* in kcal mol ⁻¹ , ΔS^* in cal mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹													
	15°			20°			25°			30°			35°	
ΔH^*	ΔG^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*	ΔS^*		
10	22.5	20.5	7.0	20.4	7.0	20.4	7.0	20.4	7.0	20.4	7.0	7.0		
20	22.0	20.6	5.0	20.6	5.0	20.6	4.9	20.5	5.0	20.5	5.1	5.1		
30	21.6	20.7	3.1	20.7	3.1	20.7	3.1	20.6	3.2	20.6	3.2	3.2		
40	21.1	20.8	0.8	20.8	0.7	20.8	0.8	20.8	0.8	20.8	0.8	0.8		
50	20.9	20.9	-0.2	20.9	-0.3	20.9	-0.2	20.9	-0.2	20.9	-0.1	-0.1		
60	20.6	21.0	-1.3	21.0	-1.3	21.0	-1.2	21.0	-1.3	21.0	-1.2	-1.2		
70	20.2	21.0	-3.0	21.0	-2.9	21.1	-3.0	21.1	-3.1	21.1	-3.0	-3.0		

percentage of acetone. If the decrease is attributed to the solvation change then one of the states (reactant or transition state) is more prone to solvation than the other.

Since the transition state is a large dipolar anion with two units of negative charge on it, its solvation will increase with increasing percentage of acetone compared to the initial state. Naturally E_a value will decrease. However, it is important to note that the rate is not increasing. This may be on account of the fact that the reaction is entropy dependent.

Thermodynamic parameters: The thermodynamic activation parameters, ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* were calculated by usual methods. They have been listed in Table 3. It is to be noted that ΔG^* increases very slowly as the proportion of acetone is increased. This shows that the stability of the transition state is very little affected by the addition of organic cosolvent. The variation in ΔS^* and ΔH^* obeys the Barclay-Butler rule¹⁴ resulting a straight line plot with slope equal to 750. This slope, also known as Glunwald¹⁵ solvent stabilisation operator, predicts, the absence of the strong interaction when the value is near about 800. This suggests that only little interaction when acetone is taking place.

Effect of ionic strength: The small effect of ionic strength suggests that the reaction is not of ion-ion but ion-molecule type.

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First Dissociation Constant of *o*-Phthalic Acid from 283.15 to 323.15 K

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RECENTLY we have shown that the use of modified Davies equation gives as accurate values of pK_1 and pK_2 of *o*-phthalic acid as is obtained by the use of full Debye-Hückel equation¹. Modified Davies equation (1) and the independence of β_1 ,

$$\log \gamma_1 = -\frac{AZ_1^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + \beta_1 \mu \tag{1}$$

therein on the composition of ionic atmosphere, at least upto $\mu = 0.1$ mol kg⁻¹ was applied by Sinha *et al.*² to determine pK_1 of oxalic acid from 283.15 to 323.15 K in steps of 5 K and for this, cell (C-1) was used.

In this note an attempt has been made to test indirectly the accuracy of the pK_1 values of oxalic acid obtained by them. Simultaneously it has been shown that modified Davies equation gives the values of activity coefficient fairly accurately at least upto $\mu = 0.1$ mol kg⁻¹. For this, the cell (C-2) was set up.

Experimental

KCl (G.R.) free from Br⁻ and *o*-phthalic acid (G.R.) on analysis by standard methods were found to be respectively 99.99 and 99.95% pure. All weighings were corrected for buoyancy. The stoichio-